

Toxicity Assessment of Cypermethrin, Deltamethrin, Difenoconazole, and Lambda-cyhalothrin on the Physiological Behavior of Commercial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Strain and their Dissipation kinetics during Alcoholic Fermentation

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Abstract: In modern viticulture, pesticides are widely used to enhance crop yield and manage grapevine diseases. However, their accumulation in grape-derived products raises concerns about potential risks to human health. This study aims to evaluate the impact of three pyrethroid insecticides (cypermethrin (CP), deltamethrin (DLM), and lambda-cyhalothrin (LTC)) and one triazole fungicide (difenoconazole (DFZ))—at levels equivalent to their EU maximum residue limits (MRLs)—on the growth of the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*-X16 yeast strain during alcoholic fermentation. Additionally, the study investigates how commercial yeast contributes to the dissipation of these pesticides during fermentation, focusing on the yeast's ability to degrade fortified pesticide residues. The results indicate that while these pesticides slightly impact yeast growth and sugar metabolism, they do not impair the fermentative activity of *S. cerevisiae*. Maximum dissipation of CP and LTC occurred at 8 days, while DLM and DFZ reached their highest dissipation at 18 days, with dissipation rates (K_{diss}) of 0.062, 0.024, 0.267, and 0.262 days⁻¹, respectively. These findings shed light on the role of commercial oenological yeast starters in both conducting fermentation and reducing pesticide residues in wine production.

Keywords: Food analysis; Wine; Alcoholic Fermentation; *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; Pesticide Dissipation; Pyrethroid; Triazole; QuEChERS; LC-MS/MS.

1. Introduction

Grapes are one of the most widely cultivated fruits. They are served fresh and in processed forms (wine, raisins, grape juice, etc.), where wine production uses about 50% of cultivated grapes (Schusterova *et al.*, 2021). However, grapevines are vulnerable to infection by pathogenic microorganisms, causing significant annual economic losses in the global wine sector (Rienth *et al.*, 2021). These losses are mainly attributable to downy mildew (*Plasmopara viticola*), powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*) and gray mold (*Botrytis cinerea*) (Scariot, Delamare and Echeverrigaray, 2022). The occurrence of these fungal diseases in/on grapes represents a critical challenge for the

global wine industry. Therefore, to guarantee sustainable production and fruit quality, viticulture depends on the application of pesticides in relatively significant quantities and on a regular basis (Edder *et al.*, 2009; Čuš *et al.*, 2010). Despite their ability to effectively combat diseases and improve crop yields (Xiao *et al.*, 2020), pesticides' overuse endangers food security, human health by interfering with the food chain, and environmental biodiversity (Fleurat-Lessard *et al.*, 2007; Rantsiou *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, pesticides are often applied without obeying the suppliers' recommendations, which results in the long-term persistence of organic residues in must and wine exceeding the authorized levels (Ramadan *et al.*, 2020).

In order to regulate the pesticide levels in plant-based foodstuffs, national and international organizations, mainly the European Commission (EC), U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and Codex Alimentarius have established "maximum residue levels" (MRLs) as the legal amount of pesticides. In general, there is no risk of exceeding MRLs when pesticides are used in accordance with GAP (Good Agricultural Practices), but inappropriate use of these hazardous chemical materials could result in considerable amounts of dangerous residues accumulating in the environment (Fleurat-Lessard *et al.*, 2007). The MRLs of pesticides in grapes typically range between 0.01 and 10 mg.kg⁻¹, depending on their type (Bakırcı *et al.*, 2014; Scariot, Delamare and Echeverrigaray, 2022). According to the EU database, grapes are one of the most contaminated crops, acquiring multiple doses of pesticides during the cultivation period (*EU Pesticides Database (v.2.1)*, 2022). In addition, the Environmental Working Group (EWG) ranked grapes sixth on the "Dirty Dozen" list in 2021 and seventh in 2012 for the quantity of pesticide residues detected in them (EWG, 2022).

The direct consequence of the widespread use of pesticides in viticulture is the negative impact of persistent chemical residues on alcoholic fermentation during the winemaking process. During this process, the yeasts are the most important agents that essentially turn sugar into ethanol and CO₂ (Russo *et al.*, 2019). Pesticide residues can severely limit the viability of yeasts, particularly *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, leading to stuck, sluggish, delayed, or blocked fermentation during winemaking process which outcomes cloudy wines (Sala *et al.*, 1996; Caboni and Cabras, 2010; Francesca *et al.*, 2016; Russo *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the presence of pesticides at legally permissible levels during the fermentation process can have a significant impact on the flavor and aromatic profile of various beverages (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014; Navarro *et al.*, 2015; EL Dana, Hayar and Colosio, 2021). Fermentation interruptions are one of the major difficult challenges in winemaking due to the high risk of economic losses and wine quality deterioration (Capozzi *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, fungicide residues can affect the fermentative process of yeasts directly or indirectly (Walker and Stewart, 2016). They can lead to modifications in the cell structure (Sieiro-Sampedro *et al.*, 2020), metabolism, development (González-Rodríguez, Cancho-Grande and Simal-Gándara, 2011; Kong *et al.*, 2016), population diversity (typification), and final counts of yeast (Kosel, Raspor and Čadež, 2019), delaying fermentation (Agarbati *et al.*, 2019; Oliva *et al.*, 2020). The relationship between *S. cerevisiae* and its environment have been the subject of numerous studies since it is the most used yeast in the production of alcoholic beverages. These studies show that *S. cerevisiae* cells are able to lower the concentration of a wide range of organic (fatty acids) (Pradelles *et al.*, 2008) and inorganic contaminants (Razmkhab *et al.*, 2002) during the winemaking process. Moreover, pesticide residues are also mostly dissipated during the alcoholic fermentation step (An *et al.*, 2018). In Lebanon, few investigations are done to study the effectiveness of a commercial strain of *S. cerevisiae* on pesticide elimination

during the winemaking process. Then, this research project presents the effect of *S. cerevisiae* on the mixture of 4 molecule pesticides mostly detected in Lebanese grapes: cypermethrin, deltamethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin (pyrethroid group) and difenoconazole (triazole family) (Sandikly, Hayar and Millet, 2019).

The primary objectives of this study are to: (i) evaluate the efficiency of the QuEChERS method for extracting four pesticide residues from wine and analyze them using liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), (ii) examine the growth dynamics and fermentation kinetics of the commercial oenological yeast strain *S. cerevisiae* (X16) during alcoholic fermentation in the presence of a mixture of the four fortified pesticides, and (iii) assess the dissipation kinetics of these pesticides throughout the fermentation process.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Equipment

An Agilent 1200SL LC system with a Tandem 3200 Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (AB SCIEX, Dublin, CA, USA) equipped with an electrospray chemical ionization (ESI) source that may mix positive and negative ionization modes was used for the LC-MS/MS analysis. The analytical column was a reverse-phase analytical C₁₈ (150 × 2 mm × 2.5 μm) (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) equipped with a guard column. Other equipment included a stove (Heraeus Incubator), BioTek ELx800 microplate reader, a shaker (Multi Stack, Shaking; LabTech, Sorisole (BG), Italy), a Z 300 Universal Centrifuge (Hermle Labor Technik GmbH), a spectrophotometer (U-200, Hitachi, Fukuoka, Japan), an optical Nikon microscope, and a Neubauer chamber (Merck, Madrid, Spain).

2.2. Chemicals and Reagents

Cypermethrin (CP), deltamethrin (DLM), difenoconazole (DFZ), and lambda-cyhalothrin (LTC) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer GmbH, Augsburg, Germany, with verified purity above 98.9%. These pesticides were selected based on the results of a sampling campaign in Lebanese grape cultivation (Sandikly, Hayar and Millet, 2019), consultations with agricultural engineers, enologists, and suppliers in Lebanon, as well as author findings (Abdallah et al., 2014; Cabras & Angioni, 2000; Dumitriu (Gabur), Teodosiu, & V. Cotea, 2021). The chemical structures of the four pesticides used are given in **Figure 1**. Their physical and chemical characteristics are given in **Table 1**. The individual working solution of each pesticide (10 mg.l⁻¹) was prepared from standard stock solutions (1000 mg.l⁻¹) in acetonitrile (ACN, Sigma-Aldrich International GmbH) and stored at -18°C. All standard solutions were maintained in the dark at 4°C.

Figure 1. Chemical structure diagrams of: (a) cypermethrin, (b) deltamethrin, (c) difenoconazole, and (d) lambda-cyhalothrin.

Analytical grade solvents and reagents, minerals, and oligo-elements were obtained by Sigma-Aldrich International GmbH (Munich, Schnellendorf, Germany). Anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4), sodium chloride (NaCl), and primary secondary amine (PSA) were supplied by Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The active commercial dry yeast *S. cerevisiae* (LAFFORT l'oenologie par nature/ZYMAFLORE[®]) was awarded by Chateau Kefraya, a Lebanese vineyard castle. The media culture, Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose (YPD/YEPD), was supplied by Darmstadt, Germany. A MilliQ water purification system was used to generate laboratory ultra-pure water (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA).

Table 1. Physical and Chemical Characteristics of the four fortified pesticides in synthetic grape juice.

Chemical Group	Molecule	Molecular Formula	Use	Log K_{ow}^1	Molecular Weight (g mol ⁻¹)	Solubility in Water (g l ⁻¹) at 20°C
		Cas number	Mode of Action			

Pyrethroids	Cypermethrin	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ C ₁₂ NO ₃ 52315-07-8	Insecticide Contact	6.6	416.30	0.0090
	Deltamethrin	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Br ₂ NO ₃ 52918-63-5	Insecticide Contact	4.6	505.20	0.0002
	Lambda-cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃ 91465-08-6	Insecticide Contact	6.8	449.85	0.0050
Triazole	Difenoconazole	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ C ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ 119446-68-3	Fungicide Systemic	4.4	406.26	15.000

¹Octanol-water partition coefficient

2.3. Yeast strains and preculture conditions

Rehydration of the commercial *S. cerevisiae* yeast was followed in 10x sterile water for 30 min at 37°C. The yeast cells were pre-cultured on YPD agar (2% glucose, 2% peptone, 1% yeast extract, and 2% agar), without agitation at 22°C for 48 hours. A starter culture of a yeast strain was prepared by inoculating a single colony into 100 ml of synthetic media made up of: 50 g glucose, 1 g yeast extract, 2 g (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.3 g citric acid, 5 g L-malic acid, 5 g L-tartaric acid, 0.4 g MgSO₄, and 5 g KH₂PO₄ for 48 hours at 22°C in an incubator-shaker at 150 rpm.min⁻¹ (Feghali *et al.*, 2019).

2.4. Alcoholic fermentation conditions and sampling

The fermentations were carried out in a synthetic grape juice medium (SGJ) that mimics grape composition. The SGJ media (expressed per 100 mL) made up of: 12 g glucose, 12 g fructose, 0.4 g L-tartaric acid, 0.03 g citric acid, 0.5 g L-malic acid, 0.2 g KH₂PO₄, 0.02 g MgSO₄, 0.03 g (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.03 g C₆H₁₂O₆, 0.24 g CaCO₃, 0.01 g anaerobic factors, 0.05 g turbicel, 0.6 mL amino acid, 0.1 mL vitamins, 0.02 mL 10% SO₂ solution, 0.1 mL oligo-elements (expressed per mg.l⁻¹): 750 KH₂PO₄, 500 KH₂SO₄, 250 MgSO₄.7H₂O, 155 CaC₁₂.2H₂O, 200 NaCl, 4 MnSO₄.H₂O, 4 ZnSO₄, 1 CuSO₄.5H₂O, 1 KI, 0.4 CoC₁₂.6H₂O, 1 H₃BO₃, and 1 (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄ (EL Dana *et al.*, 2021). Liquid cultures were incubated at 22°C using an orbital incubator-shaker at 150 rpm.min⁻¹. The pH of the SGJ medium was adjusted to 3.2 ± 0.3 with phosphate-citrate buffer. The mixture of pesticides was spiked according to their corresponding EU-MRLs; 0.5, 0.2, 3, and 0.2 mg.kg⁻¹ for CP, DLM, DFZ, and LTC, respectively. After 24 hours of pesticide addition, 1 x 10⁷ cells.ml⁻¹ of pre-cultured yeast cells were added to each 100 ml fermentation Erlenmeyer. In addition to the control carried out under the same conditions, the presence of only acetonitrile solvent was conducted to assess the toxicity of the solvent. All assays were carried out under aseptic conditions and in five replicates. The progress of the fermentation was monitored by extrapolating CO₂ release from weight loss measures throughout the process. Samples were collected at intervals from each flask, and yeast growth OD₆₀₀, viability of cells (%CFU.cell⁻¹), biomass (g.l⁻¹), and residual sugar content (g.l⁻¹) were studied to monitor the effect of the mixture of pesticides on the growth kinetics of *S. cerevisiae*. The dissipation kinetics of pesticide concentration by LC-MS/MS was also investigated.

2.5. Alcoholic fermentation analysis

The dinitrosalicylic acid method (DNS) was used to determine the amount of reducing sugar (g.l^{-1}) during fermentation (Miller, 1959). Growth curves in the SGJ medium were measured at $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ using a spectrometer and transformed into concentration using an established proportional standard curve (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). The dry yeast cell weight was determined gravimetrically in three replicates by placing the wet biomass at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until a constant weight was reached. The biomass concentration is then calculated by subtracting the filter mass before and after drying from the sample volume and expressed in (g.l^{-1}) (Sarris *et al.*, 2009; Terpou *et al.*, 2019). The viability of the yeast ($\%\text{CFU.ml}^{-1}$) was rapidly evaluated by an optical Nikon microscope using the alkaline methylene blue staining method in the Neubauer chamber (Bonora and Mares, 1982). A hemocytometer (depth of 0.2 mm) was employed to count the yeast cells (Shurson, 2018).

2.6. Evaluation of the Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

In a preliminary evaluation, the impact of specified concentrations of the evaluated pesticides was examined on *S. cerevisiae* yeast strain using a micro-dilution approach. For this purpose, a serial 2-fold dilution of the fortified pesticides was made in YPD broth containing yeast of approximately 1×10^7 cells. ml^{-1} in 96-well culture plates. After this time, plates were incubated for 48 hours at 28°C in the dark and then analyzed at OD_{600} , and the first well in the series of dilutions that did not show growth was taken into consideration as the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) (Kosel, Raspor and Čadež, 2019).

2.7. Pesticide extraction and clean-up

The four fortified pesticides were extracted from the synthetic wine following the modified QuEChERS cleanup technique (Jiang *et al.*, 2009). The chosen technique was determined by the results of recovery experiments conducted using three alternative techniques (preliminary results). After centrifuging the samples for 5 minutes at 4000 rpm at 4°C to separate the yeasts, 10 g of supernatant was weighed into a 50-mL propylene centrifuge tube; 5 mL of acetonitrile ACN was added, and the mixture was vigorously shaken for 1 minute before adding 4 g of MgSO_4 and 3 g of NaCl. For 1 minute, the tube was manually shaken. Afterward, the tube was subjected to centrifugation for 8 min at 4000 rpm. Then a dispersive-SPE cleanup was done by transferring 1 mL of supernatant to a dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) minicentrifuge tube containing 150 mg of MgSO_4 and 50 mg of PSA. The tube was shaken for 1 minute, then centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatant was then filtered through a $0.20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter and transferred into a glass vial to be analyzed by (LC-MS/MS). The final sample extracts were diluted with acetonitrile as necessary to fit them within the quantitative range of the calibration curves.

2.8. Liquid Chromatography coupled to Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC/MS-MS) analytical conditions

The LC-MS/MS analysis was carried out using the Agilent LC-MS/MS. The mobile phase A: methanol; mobile phase B: gradient methanol buffered with 5 mM ammonium acetate; injection volume $5\text{ }\mu\text{L}$; flow rate 0.4 ml min^{-1} ; total run time of 30 min; mobile phase gradients: 2% B to 100% of B over 12 min, held at 100% B until 20 min then decreased to 2% B at 25.01 min; the column was maintained at 25°C . Data acquisition was performed in multiple

reaction monitoring (MRM) transition; ion spray voltage of 5 kV and a gas temperature of 500°C. Nitrogen gas was used as collision gas and a nebulizer curtain gas. The optimized parameters for the pesticide's qualification and quantification are shown in **Table 2**. The collision energy (CE), the declustering potential (DP), the entrance potential (EP), and the collision cell exit potential (CXP) were optimized for each target analyte pesticide.

Table 2. Precursor, transition ions and source parameters for the four pesticide residues analyzed by the LC-MS/MS method.

Pesticide	RT	Transition		DP	CE	CXP	Transition		DP	CE	CXP		
	(Min)	Q1 (m/z)	→				Q2 (m/z)	→				(Volts)	
Cypermethrin	21.97	416.1	→	191.9	36	27	18	416.1	→	127.0	36	43	0
Deltamethrin	22.87	506.9	→	181.3	51	23	8	506.9	→	280.6	51	51	14
Difenoconazole	19.27	406.2	→	251.1	96	37	14	406.2	→	337.0	96	37	14
Lambda-cyhalothrin	22.37	467.1	→	225.0	41	23	8	467.1	→	141.1	35	30	10

Conditions	Content
Instrument	Model AB Sciex 3200 QTRAP LC-MS/MS SYSTEM
Column	C ₁₈ column, Phenomenex Analytical Synergi, 150 x 2 mm, 2.5 µm particle size
Flow rate	Gradient elution program at 0.4 ml min ⁻¹
Source temperature	500°C – 5 kV
Ion Spray Potential-Mode	Electron Spray Ionization, Positive Mode

2.9. Pesticide dissipation decay model

The experimental data were fitted to a mathematical model to determine the dissipation rate, regression equations, and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of residues in each winemaking process. Data is analyzed using R software (Majed, Hayar and Zeitoun, 2021):

$$C_t = C_0 \times e^{-kt} \quad (1)$$

Where:

C_t = the residual concentration at time t (days) (mg kg⁻¹)

C_0 = the initial fortified concentration (mg kg⁻¹)

k = dissipation rate of the molecule/slope of the exponential regression curve (day⁻¹)

To calculate the time required for pesticide residue to decrease to half its initial concentration C_i , the following equation was used:

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k} \quad (2)$$

Processing factor (PF) can be used to express the change in pesticide residue levels at the end of fermentation (Kittelmann *et al.*, 2022). It is calculated from the ratio of the spiked pesticide concentration in raw product to the residue concentration in the processed products. Pesticide residue levels decreased throughout processing if the PF value below one. The following equation can be used to calculate the processing factor (PF) (Pan, 2018):

$$PF = \frac{\text{Residue level at the end of processed Agricultural product (mg.kg}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Initial levels in synthetic grape juice at the beginning of fermentation (mg.kg}^{-1}\text{)}} \quad (3)$$

2.10. Statistical analysis

For statistical analysis, the data were loaded into Microsoft Office 2022 and R software version 4.2.1 (p -value estimation; significant differences were assigned to values of $p \leq 0.05$). All reported values are the means \pm standard deviation (SD) of five replicates.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Method validation

Complying with EU SANTE/12682/2019 guidelines (Guidance SANTE/12682/2019, 2019). Linearity (R^2), mean recovery (RM%), repeatability ($RSD_r\%$), reproducibility ($RSD_{RW}\%$), and the limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) parameters are established.

The linear regression of the calibration curves had a correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.99$). The LODs (1-2 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and LOQs (4-6 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) for the tested pesticides were much lower than the EU-MRLs for wine grapes. As a result, the method can be used to check for MRL compliance. To establish the method's accuracy and precision, the recovery results' $RSD_r\%$ and $RSD_{RW}\%$ are used.

To assess recovery, matrix blanks (10 g) were fortified with three concentration levels of pesticide standard solution. On separate days, five replicates of each fortification level were prepared. After fortification, the samples were left at room temperature for 30 minutes to allow the pesticide to be evenly incorporated into the matrix. Then, QuEChERS was carried out, followed by (LC-MS/MS) analysis. For the method to be satisfactory for pesticide analysis, the recovery values should be between 70 and 120% with a relative standard deviation $RSD\%$ less than 20% (Guidance SANTE/12682/2019, 2019). The recovery means in our study ranged from 76 to 98% with $RSD\% < 20\%$ for all values in Error! Reference source not found..

Table 3. Average of recovery data (RM%), repeatability ($RSD_r\%$) and reproducibility ($RSD_{RW}\%$), quantification limits (LOD and LOQ), and linearity for the four pesticides at the three fortification levels ($n = 5$ at each level) in SGJ medium.

Compound	LOD	LOQ	Level Spiking (0.05 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)			Level Spiking (0.1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)			Level Spiking (0.5 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		
			RM	RSD_r	RSD_{RW}	RM	RSD_r	RSD_{RW}	RM	RSD_r	RSD_{RW}
			($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Cypermethrin	0.002	0.006	89	12	14	89	11	14	91	13	15
Deltamethrin	0.001	0.004	81	11	13	79	9	12	86	6	10
Difenoconazole	0.002	0.006	97	13	14	98	10	10	98	9	12
Lambda-cyhalothrin	0.001	0.004	76	12	14	77	11	14	79	9	11

3.2. Fermentation kinetics of the *S. cerevisiae* strain in synthetic grape juice medium

Synthetic grape juice fermentation was completed after 25 days. The behavior of the yeast during alcoholic fermentation (biomass production ($\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) and reducing sugar metabolism ($\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) is represented in Error! Reference source not found.. During fermentation, the pH was maintained at 3.16 ± 0.3 . The yeast growth followed a traditional bacterial growth curve (Hayek *et al.*, 2020) with four distinct phases: latent phase (adaptation phase), exponential phase (constant rate of cell division), stationary phase (where yeast stop replicating due to unfavorable conditions),

and ultimately death phase (cell viability loss). Due to the use of pre-culture and starter, yeast overcomes its nearly nonexistent latency phase one day of fermentation. A linear pace with a maximum and constant growth rate of 0.1 h^{-1} was typical of the exponential growth phase, lasting between 1 and 5 days. Following that, the yeast cells undergo a 21-day stationary phase, during which their biomass and cell concentration reduce slightly. Throughout the fermentation, the biomass concentration and sugar consumption are in perfect synergy, particularly during the exponential phase when sugar concentrations are rapidly declining Error! Reference source not found..

Figure 2. Kinetic of total residual Sugar (g l^{-1}) (●) and biomass production (yeast dry weight (g l^{-1})) (■) of *S. cerevisiae* during AF of SGJ.

3.3. Effect of a mixture of pesticides on the growth of *S. cerevisiae* during alcoholic fermentation

In a preliminary assay, we monitored the growth of yeast cells in the presence of different concentrations of pesticides. According to MIC tests, CP, DLM, DFZ, and LTC have MIC values of MRL. The yeast cells showed growth up to MRL value for each pesticide. Therefore, the lethal dose of EU-MRL in wine grapes for each of the four pesticides was selected to assess their effects on yeast and the ability of yeast to dissipate pesticides during alcoholic fermentation (*EU Pesticides Database (v.2.2) Pesticide Residue(s) and Maximum Residue Levels (Mg/Kg)*, 2022).

Yeast viability

The viability ($\% \text{CFU} \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$) of yeast cells at three different modalities is depicted in **Figure 3**. Acetonitrile had insignificant impact on the viability of the yeast when compared to the control ($p > 0.05$) throughout fermentation. While the results showed that during the first 5 days, pesticide mixture-enriched showed a significant difference on yeast viability ($p < 0.05$), decreasing from 88.5 to 86.4%. Cell viability assays are used to evaluate the cellular toxicity exerted by the mixture of pesticides on yeast cells. The obtained data revealed that during the yeast multiplication phase, the mixture of pesticides exhibited a cytotoxic effect on yeast cells. This reduction is related to redox deficiency, leading to oxidative stress and the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), damaging a variety of biomolecules, including proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids (Kouretas *et al.*, 2013). The mixture of four pesticides appears to be

stressing yeast cells by inhibiting ergosterol in their cell walls. This allegation was used by (Cordero-Bueso, Arroyo and Valero, 2014) to relate the decrease in concentration and viability of yeast cells to the triazole penconazole fungicide's capacity to block ergosterol biosynthesis in yeast cells. (Gava et al., 2021) also reported that triazoles suppress ergosterol production in phytopathogenic fungi and in oenological yeasts. Ergosterol, a key component of yeast cell membranes, controls the fluidity, permeability, and activity of membrane-associated proteins (Abe and Hiraki, 2009). The ergosterol production pathway is a primary target and is required for fungal growth and viability (Jordá and Puig, 2020). Besides, liposoluble pesticide molecules may alter plasma membrane function as a selective barrier and enzyme matrix, causing the transmembrane H⁺-gradient to dissipate and the transmembrane passage of nutrients and other solutes to be restricted (Cabral *et al.*, 2003).

From day 5 until the end of fermentation, during the stationary phase of the yeast, the mixture of pesticides shows insignificant differences when compared to the control ($p > 0.05$). Interestingly, despite the loss of viability profile in yeast during the early stages of pesticide (0–5 days), the yeast strain was able to adapt to new conditions in which an exponential growth phase was initiated in both the absence and presence of pesticides. According to (Ribeiro and Ver, 2000), yeast strains employed in fermentation are more resistant to stress factors and have a high potential to respond to environmental disturbances. It has been demonstrated that yeast cells in their stationary stage may be resistant to the presence of pesticides, particularly pyrethroids that induce oxidative stress on yeast cells, because the activity of antioxidant enzymes is lower at this stage (Krzepińko and Świącilo, 2007). The ability of yeast cells to accumulate ergosterol reserves in the cell membrane may be the explanation for their growth resumption between day 5 and 8. High levels of pesticide residues during fermentation may first induce reduced cell growth, followed by the resumption of microbe growth since ergosterol content is crucial for yeast stress adaptability (Ribeiro and Ver, 2000)

Table 4.

Figure 3. Average viable *S. cerevisiae* cells in (%CFU ml⁻¹), untreated control (P0), acetonitrile-enriched (P0-ACN), and the mixture of pesticide-enriched (P-ACN) media during AF of SGJ medium.

Similar adaptive responses of *S. cerevisiae* during fermentation have been described in the literature by (Jawich *et al.*, 2006) to the presence of triazole penconazole at concentrations twice the MRL. The short-term viability loss was highly dependent on cell physiology: exponential cells were sensitive to pesticide-induced mortality, but cells entering the stationary phase, particularly those in the early stationary phase, were substantially more resistant to pesticides. This can be explained by the ability of pyrethroids like CP and DLM to delay the growth of *S. cerevisiae* by prolonging its lag phase (Krzepiłko and Świącilo, 2007) or by the pesticide's probable degradation, accumulating hazardous intermediate compounds. This is consistent with the antimicrobial effect of DLM's toxic metabolite (3-phenoxybenzaldehyde) (Tang *et al.*, 2020), which is degraded by *Streptomyces aureus* in conditions similar to fermentation (anaerobic conditions) (Cycoń, Żmijowska and Piotrowska-Seget, 2014).

Yeast biomass production and reducing sugar metabolism

The biomass analysis for the three modalities was demonstrated in **Table 4**. Similarly, the addition of acetonitrile has no effect on the biomass production of yeast cells throughout AF ($p > 0.05$). Yeast cells exhibited the typical growth pattern of microorganisms produced in the culture broth of the three modalities. An exponential phase, a stationary phase, and a decline or death phase were all observed. The inhibitory activity of the mixture of four pesticides on biomass production was not evident throughout the mid-exponential phase (0–5 days) and was only detectable once growth assumed the post-exponential and stationary phase. The yeast biomass was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than that of the control during the stationary phase. At the end of fermentation, the final biomass of the

yeast spiked with a mixture of pesticides decreased from 7.6 to 7.1 g.l⁻¹. Thus far, *Aspergillus niger* YAT strain show reduction in biomass in the presence of the main metabolite of cypermethrin's degradation, 3-phenoxybenzoic acid 3-PBA, with no effect in the presence of cypermethrin (Deng *et al.*, 2015).

The pesticides' negative effects are potentially caused by modifying the hydrophobic interactions between pesticides and yeast on the cell surface and perhaps altering the membrane protein structures, increasing cell membrane permeability, and making it easier for chemicals to enter the cell (González-Rodríguez, Cancho-Grande and Simal-Gándara, 2011). Tebuconazole, belonging to the triazole group, reduced yeast biomass growth at doses above its MRL (González-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, (Sieiro-Sampedro *et al.*, 2020) found that tetraconazole active substances at twice the MRL level have detrimental effects on cell concentration, viability, and biomass of *S. cerevisiae* Lalvin T73TM yeast during the stationary phase. These findings are consistent with azole chemicals' general inhibitory action on the conversion of lanosterol to ergosterol in yeast cell membranes (Ji *et al.*, 2000). It was noticed that pyrethroids and triazole pesticides affect *S. cerevisiae* growth in such a way that growth rate and final biomass production are slightly affected, with a minimal effect on the overall fermentation process. These findings oppose those reported by (Oliva *et al.*, 2020) in studies including the following fungicides: famoxadone, fenhexamid, fluquinconazole, kresoxim-methyl, quinoxifen, and trifloxystrobin, belonging to different chemical groups proving that treated wine samples exhibited higher cell counts compared to untreated samples.

However, for the fermentable sugar consumption in the samples treated with a mixture of four pesticides **Table 4**, acetonitrile-enriched media utilized the same amount of sugar throughout fermentation as the control ($p > 0.05$), demonstrating that the solvent employed to dissolve the pesticide has no effect on the characteristics of yeast sugar catabolism. In pesticide-enriched media, there was an increase in sugar consumption ($p < 0.05$), and noticeably higher quantities of sugars were assimilated (86.17%) in the SGJ by yeast cells compared to the untreated control (77.63%). In all three modalities, yeast was able to easily ferment the synthetic grape juice since invertase, the enzyme that decomposes sugar, is found in the yeast cell wall and uses sucrose to initiate fermentation (Navarro *et al.*, 2015). However, sugar was utilized faster in alcoholic fermentation in the presence of a mixture of pesticides. Similarly, the addition of pyrimethanil fungicide during the fermentation of wine increases sugar consumption in the first few days of fermentation (Čuš and Raspor, 2008). The different consumption of sugars between the modalities with or without pesticides seems due to the respiratory inhibition role of pesticides, causing the enhancement of fermentation activity by speeding up glycolysis (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014), increasing sugar consumption, and leading to a longer period for the yeast inoculum to adapt (Arroyo-López, Querol and Barrio, 2009).

Table 4. The effect of acetonitrile and the fortified mixture of pesticides on the biomass concentration (g l⁻¹) and total residual sugar (%) during AF of the SGJ medium.

	Time (Days)	P ₀	P ₀ -ACN	P-ACN
Biomass (g l ⁻¹)	T ₀	1.40 (±0.02)	1.37 (±0.01)	1.42 (±0.10)
	T ₅	8.23 (±0.07)	8.01 (±0.18)	7.95* (±0.20)
	T ₈	10.79 (±0.02)	10.71 (±0.09)	10.31* (±0.24)
	T ₁₃	8.56 (±0.17)	8.27* (±0.11)	7.71* (±0.33)
	T ₁₇	8.24 (±0.22)	8.37 (±0.42)	7.68 (±0.40)
	T ₂₅	7.64 (±0.22)	7.45 (±0.08)	7.09* (±0.17)
	Residual Sugar (%)	T ₀	99.54 (±0.71)	99.68 (±0.44)

T ₅	70.72 (±1.82)	78.10* (±1.56)	48.15* (±1.67)
T ₈	59.51 (±1.21)	57.23 (±2.27)	34.90* (±2.00)
T ₁₃	38.35 (±4.77)	40.01 (±4.63)	21.80* (±2.69)
T ₁₇	28.27 (±3.89)	27.40 (±4.61)	14.94* (±0.98)
T ₂₅	22.37 (±3.34)	25.23 (±3.85)	13.83* (±2.69)

* Significant level: ($\alpha = 0.05$); Mean \pm SD Standard Deviation of five replicates; P₀ (untreated control); P₀-ACN acetonitrile-enriched; P-ACN mixture of pesticide-enriched media.

The evolution of fermentation was controlled by the quantity of CO₂ and by weight loss measures throughout the process. Due to the large number of yeast cells produced, the fermentation process followed a consistent pattern and lasted 25 days in all assays. The impact of pesticides on the yeast strain's fermentative activity was measured by the strain's ability to tolerate these compounds while maintaining its fermentative performance. This appears to indicate that the mixture of four pesticide molecules has a significant effect on sugar consumption and yeast biomass but insignificant effect on cell viability at the end of fermentation or AF kinetics, as previously reported by other authors studying the same yeast and other triazole and dicarboximide fungicides (Cabras *et al.*, 1999; Ochiai *et al.*, 2002). This is in correlation with earlier established findings, as (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014) investigated the fermentative kinetics of fungicides and found that they had no influence on the kinetics of must fermentation but did result in a slight reduction in biomass concentration. According to research on pesticides and their effects on *S. cerevisiae* yeasts, three main factors appear to determine whether a pesticide molecule has an inhibitory effect on yeast activity: chemical structure and site of action (cell membrane).

3.4. Dissipation Kinetics of Pesticide residues by yeast cells during alcoholic fermentation

Pesticide dissipation by yeast cell during alcoholic fermentation depended on the target pesticide. The dissipation kinetics of pesticides during alcoholic fermentation of *S. cerevisiae* strains was investigated. As shown in **Figure 4.**, residues gradually decrease during alcoholic fermentation. *S. cerevisiae* yeast strain was able to remove pesticides applied at concentrations equal to their EU-MRLs (*EU Pesticides Database (v.2.2) Pesticide Residue(s) and Maximum Residue Levels (Mg/Kg).*, 2022). The residual amount of pesticides reached values < LOD after 8 days for CP and LTC, and after 18 days for DLM and DFZ. (Saied *et al.*, 2021) showed that the bacterial degradation of CP was time-dependent by proving that soil-isolated bacterial strains exhibit maximum degradation of 2500 ppm of CP after 8 days. The SGJ started alcoholic fermentation after one day of pesticide fortification. During the first fermentation period (0-5 days), during the exponential phase of yeast development, the DLM concentration significantly decreases in synthetic wine by 84%, and the other three pesticides' concentrations decrease by about 60% **Figure 4.** In current experiments, the largest reduction in pesticides took place in the first days of exposure; the dissipation most probably occurred during the yeast's multiplication phase, with complete dissipation at the stationary phase. These findings were explained by the simultaneous occurrence of fungal biodegradation of the pesticides (Pinto *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, in *S. cerevisiae* stationary phase cultures, the elimination capability of yeast strains on two fungicides (pyrimethanil and fenhexamid) was also observed (Bizaj, 2011).

(a) Cypermethrin

(b) Lambda-cyhalothrin

(c) Deltamethrin

(d) Difenoconazole

Figure 4. Dissipation Rate of (a) cypermethrin, (b) lambda-cyhalothrin, (c) deltamethrin, and (d) difenoconazole with their regression coefficient, respectively.

The experimental data was fitted to a dissipation mathematical model from the equation described in the **Pesticide Dissipation Decay Model** to determine the rate of residue dissipation during the alcoholic fermentation process **Table 5**. During the fermentation process, the pesticide completely dissipates; the complete elimination during this phase can be attributed to the yeast's active fermentation.

Table 5. Regression equations, dissipation rates, half-lives, processing factor and EU-MRLs (European Commission (EC), 2022) for wine grapes.

Molecule	Regression Equation	Correlation Coefficient (R ²)	Rate Constant K _{diss} ¹ (Day ⁻¹)	Half-life t _{1/2} (Day)	PF ² (± SD) ³	MRL ⁴ (mg kg ⁻¹)
Cypermethrin	C = -0.0619t + 0.5062	0.997	0.062	4.04	0.0020 (±0.00031)	0.5
Lambda-cyhalothrin	C = -0.0247t + 0.2021	0.997	0.024	4.04	0.0060 (±0.00158)	0.2
Deltamethrin	C = 0.2015e ^{-0.268t}	0.972	0.267	2.59	0.0050 (±0.00010)	0.2
Difenoconazole	C = 3e ^{-0.263t}	0.943	0.262	2.63	0.0003 (±0.00001)	3.0

¹ K_{diss} (Dissociation constant); ² Mean ± SD Standard Deviation of five replicates; ³ PF (Processing Factor); ⁴ EU-MRLs (*EU Pesticides Database (v.2.2) Pesticide Residue(s) and Maximum Residue Levels (Mg/Kg).*, 2022)

The dissipation kinetics of CP and LTC in the fermentation process followed the zero-order of kinetics (R²= 0.99). (Zaranyika, Matimati and Mushonga, 2020) demonstrated the existence of such linear pesticide degradation rates (zero-order) with different pesticide concentrations and microbial populations. On the other hand, the dissipation of DLM and DFZ followed a similar decay model; they followed the first order of kinetics (R² = 0.93). The pesticide concentrations were log-transformed, and the average of these points was used to determine the regression. The regression equations, half-lives, and rate constants were calculated, and the results are listed in **Table 5**. The half-lives of CP and LTC were similar t_{1/2}= 4.04 days. While the half-lives t_{1/2}= 2.59 and 2.63 days for DLM and DFZ, respectively. These results agreed with (Abdallah *et al.*, 2014), where the dissipation rate of DFZ obeyed a first-order kinetic reaction t_{1/2} of 0.294 day⁻¹, and fully dissipated after 18 days in or on grape berries.

After 3 days, the rapid decline (between 30 and 46%) of the initial concentration level of pesticides introduced to the culture medium can probably be attributed to their adsorption on yeast biomass. This matches prior findings on the ability of *S. cerevisiae* to remove the fungicides pyrimethanil and fenhexamid during an AF process by adsorbing toxicants rather than degrading them (Bizaj, 2011). The rapid adsorption to the cell surface followed by fungal uptake could be the explanation for pesticide removal (Pinto *et al.*, 2012). It is also influenced by the porosity of the *S. cerevisiae* cell wall as well as hydrophobic interactions between pesticides and the yeast cell wall (Morata *et al.*, 2003). Cell surface areas, volume, and cell wall thickness, along with 1,3- β-glucan content, all had an impact on yeast's adsorption abilities (Luo *et al.*, 2015). In an acidic medium with a pH of 3 similar to our alcoholic fermentation pH, the β-glucan in the yeast cells has a high affinity for toxin adsorption (Piotrowska and Masek, 2015).

The log K_{ow} of the octanol-water partition coefficient is an important factor in predicting pesticide adsorption behavior when studying the fate of chemical compounds (Wołejko *et al.*, 2016). The main factors influencing pesticide absorption or adsorption in or on microorganism cell walls are pesticide concentration and lipophilicity (Majed, Hayar and Zeitoun, 2021). The pesticide residues were distributed during AF between the liquid phase (SGJ) and the solid phase (yeast cell wall). DLM and DFZ have nearly similar log K_{ow} and elimination times, as do CP and LTC. Hydrophilic pesticides with a lower Log K_{ow} (DLM and DFZ) tend to have a lower affinity for the yeast cell wall, and the increase in yeast population could accelerate pesticide dissipation throughout fermentation (Hou *et al.*, 2020). Among the three pyrethroid insecticides studied, DLM decomposes slowly compared to CP and LTC, which could be

related to their higher molecular weight (Wolejko *et al.*, 2016). (González-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009) used this allegation to demonstrate *S. cerevisiae*'s ability to adsorb organic and inorganic contaminants via cell wall polysaccharides. These findings point to a correlation between the high log K_{ow} and the rapid dissipation rates of pesticides (Abdallah *et al.*, 2014). This suggests that the hydro-solubility of pesticide residues is proportional to their breakdown mechanism by yeast. This is in agreement with the results of other studies (Pazzirota *et al.*, 2013). The pyrethroids used (CP, DLM, and LTC) are esters and have several hydrolysis sites (Singh and Walker, 2006). The degradation of DLM in experimental wine seemed to originate from a hydrolysis reaction (Jiménez *et al.*, 2007). Pesticides with high vapor pressure and low solubility in water **Table 1** may also escape into the atmosphere, according to Henry's Law constants. This assumption was used by (Navarro *et al.*, 2015) to relate the tendency of a compound to volatilize from an aqueous solution to air in beer fermentation.

The PFs of four target pesticides were calculated during the fermentation process and are shown in **Table 5**. In fermentation, the PFs of four fungicides ranged from 0.0003 to 0.005, all less than one. According to the results, yeast cells were able to significantly dissipate the residual levels of four target fungicides in synthetic grape juice during the AF process. The findings were consistent with previous observations (Hou *et al.*, 2020), proving that yeast might break down certain pesticides and reduce residues in wine. (Čuš *et al.*, 2010) emphasized fenhexamid's affinity for the lees, remarking that no residues were detected in the liquid phase. Likewise, (Caboni, 2010) reported that pesticide reduction was due to lees' adsorption effect. Several papers investigated the behavior of pesticides from vine to wine as well as the impact of yeast on their residues (Cabras *et al.*, 1995; Angioni *et al.*, 2003; Zara, Caboni and Orro, 2011; Xiao *et al.*, 2020).

4. Conclusion

This study highlights the impact of commercial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* on a mixture of pesticides fortified to EU-MRL levels, focusing on the residues' effects on yeast growth kinetics and alcoholic fermentation. The presence of pesticides resulted in moderate yeast viability, with a notable reduction in biomass from 7.6 to 7.1 g L⁻¹ and an increase in sugar consumption efficiency from 86.17% to 77.63% by the end of fermentation. The fermentative behavior, including CO₂ production, remained consistent across control samples and those containing acetonitrile and pesticides. Pesticide residues were completely dissipated during alcoholic fermentation, following different kinetic degradation patterns. Cypermethrin (CP) and lambda-cyhalothrin (LTC) exhibited zero-order kinetics with complete dissipation within 8 days, a half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of 4.04 days, and dissipation rates (K_a) of 0.062 and 0.024 day⁻¹, respectively. Deltamethrin (DLM) and difenoconazole (DFZ) followed first-order kinetics, with complete degradation achieved in 18 days, a half-life of 2.60 days, and dissipation rates of 0.267 and 0.262 day⁻¹, respectively. The processing factors (PFs) for all four pesticides were below one, indicating the fermentation process's capacity to reduce pesticide residues effectively. These findings demonstrate the high efficiency of commercial *S. cerevisiae* yeast in both initiating fermentation and eliminating pesticide residues, specifically the pyrethroid insecticides CP, DLM, and LTC, as well as the triazole fungicide DFZ, in synthetic grape juice. This research suggests that wineries can safely use wine grapes with pesticide residues up to EU-MRL levels, as the fermentation process significantly reduces these residues. However, to further improve wine quality and mitigate potential risks to human health and non-target organisms, it remains essential to monitor pesticide residue levels in wine grapes and evaluate their effects on actual grape samples.

5. References

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